

A LOW-COST FLOW FRONT MONITORING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a sensor network consisting of three MEMS accelerometers with integrated temperature sensors was used to perform a flow front detection in a resin transfer molding (RTM) process. The applied sensor, a BMA280, is a low-cost, three-axis accelerometer with an integrated temperature sensor measuring 2 x 2 x 1 mm³. First the sensor system was validated in a RTM tool with a transparent upper mold. With visual inspection, the filling of the mold was correlated with recorded sensor signals. In another RTM tool, the sensitivity of the validated sensor system has been tested with different setups. It could be shown, that even under difficult conditions such as low resin velocities and long residence times in the tool, it was possible to gather information about the flow front propagation. With the acceleration signal and, under certain boundary conditions the temperature signal as well, the system was able to detect a propagating flow front inside a closed tool.

1 INTRODUCTION

High material costs, complicated manufacturing processes and fluctuating material properties may explain some restraints towards the use of endless fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) in automotive engineering. In a vision of the future, composite parts record their own manufacturing parameters, self-monitor their damage condition and log endured load cycles. With this sophisticated data, the obstacles mentioned above can be addressed. With their layer-by-layer design, endless FRP offer a high potential for embedding sensors and thus equipping components with the required intelligence. A commonly used process used for manufacturing automotive structures is the resin transfer molding (RTM) process, which allows the production of near-net-shaped geometries of high structural integrity. Declining mechanical properties are closely linked to the formation of weld lines, dry spots and other degrading effects. Although filling simulations offer good possibilities to calculate the resin's propagation [1], validation is still necessary because of the huge effect of environmental conditions on the raw materials [2]. Hence monitoring and optimizing process parameters is crucial to exploit the mechanical potentials of FRP further. This approach has been pursued since the 80s and has resulted in a number of good practices. Mulligan and Konstantopoulos et al. [3-4] provide a good overview of existing techniques for in-line process monitoring. Here, electromagnetic, mechanical, optical and thermo-dynamical properties have been identified as the most common sensing methods. While many of the described techniques can monitor the curing process precisely, only optical fibers and piezoelectric transducer can be used for further data acquisition in the consolidated part. First investigations show that costs for developing and integrating a sensor network can be reduced by embedding sensors that offer an added value by subsequent data-generation after the production process [5]. This leads to the conclusion that in order to develop a cost-effective sensor system for process monitoring it has to fulfill the requirement of delivering data throughout the component life cycle. Mass-produced micro electromechanical systems (MEMS) have their origin in the cost-driven market of consumer electronics and offer many different sensory functions. Gaining information about the accelerations experienced by a component enables a brought variety of possible use-cases to utilize and commercialize the recorded data in automobile applications.

Consequently, this paper investigates a sensor network consisting of MEMS accelerometers for in-line process monitoring and illustrates its potential to detect the macroscopic flow front in RTM tools. The introduced system offers an inexpensive and retrofitable alternative to complex tool designs and existing techniques for process monitoring. The embedded sensors survive the production process and can therefore be used for a variety of applications after the consolidation of the component.

2 COMPONENTS AND EQUIPMENT

2.1 Sensor Network

Fig. 1 Dimensions of BMA280 (a) and mounted BMA280 on PCB (b)

The MEMS being used is a Bosch BMA280, a three-axis accelerometer with a $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$ footprint and a height of 1 mm (Fig. 1 a). An on-board application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) converts analogue data sampled at 2 kHz into a 14 bit digital signal with an adjustable g-range from $\pm 2 \text{ g}$ to $\pm 16 \text{ g}$. Additionally, the BMA280 has an integrated temperature sensor ranging from $-40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ – $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a resolution of $0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A flexible printed circuit board (PCB) with a height of 0.2 mm has been developed and equipped with three MEMS as well as two decoupling capacitors each (Fig. 1 b). The acquired data is transmitted to an Arduino Due via a serial peripheral interface (SPI) using a standard FFC connector. The required scripts are self-developed using the official Arduino IDE. After initialization of the sensors a self-test is carried out, which detects damaged sensors and stops transmission if necessary. Using the interrupt lines offered by the Arduino and the sensors, the acceleration data is timestamped with an average deviation of $3 \text{ } \mu\text{s}$. The acceleration signal is stored in arrays and saved on a micro SD card after the measurement period.

2.2 RTM Process

In the scope of the investigations covered by this paper, two different RTM systems were used. The first unit consists of a lower aluminum mold and a transparent upper glass mold. The sprue used to initiate a band gate for continuous resin propagation towards the riser (see Fig. 2). The cavity has a dimension of $325 \times 205 \text{ mm}^2$ and has a height of 2 mm. Four layers of glass fiber multiaxial fabric resulting in a $[(-45/0/45/90)(90/-45/0/45)]_s$ layup were used for this experiment. The sensor network was placed in the neutral plane between the middle layers and stretched over the length of the tool. This leads to a location of the sensors at 4 cm, 13 cm and 22 cm distance away from the sprue. A silicone hose, positioned in a notch serves as the tool's sealing. 20 bolts are used to close the tool, tightened with 30 Nm each. Since this tool cannot be heated, the resin was heated to $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ inside the pressure pot before injection instead. The sprue side was pressurized with 5 bar and no vacuum was applied on the riser side. After injection, the resin consolidates with a holding pressure of 5 bar.

The second RTM tool is made of solid aluminum with two integrated heating cartridges in both upper and lower mold. A spacer ring, positioned between the two molds, defines the footprint and height of the sample. Five openings in the upper form can be used as sprue or risers depending on the desired test setup. Clamping devices are mounted on the side of the lower form to allow a reproducible positioning of the PCBs (Fig. 3). In the scope of this work, the chosen geometry of the specimen is a planar structure with dimensions of $280 \times 280 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$. The multiaxial glass fiber fabric is stacked

resulting in a $[(-45/0/45/90)(45/90/-45/0)]_s$ layup. The sensor network is embedded in between the middle layers with a distance of 45 mm from the lower edge. Afterwards, the tool is locked using 20 bolts, tightened with 30 Nm each. The mold is heated to 65 °C and pressurized with 4 bar on the sprue side. The air at the riser side is evacuated with a 0.10 mbar negative pressure.

Fig. 2 Experimental setup for validating flow front detection

Fig. 3 RTM tool used for process monitoring

2.3 Resin System

The matrix system used is resin grade Araldite LY 1564 with the corresponding hardener Aradur 5003-1 BD, both produced by Huntsman. Processing is carried out following a strict sequence. After intermingling of the components, a dynamic mixer is used 9.5 minutes to blend the mixture thoroughly. After degassing the resin for 4 minutes in a 0.1 mbar vacuum, the resin is put inside the pressure pot and gets injected 20 minutes after the initial contact of resin and hardener. 1:25 hours after injection, the specimen is demolded with a fiber volume content of 40 %.

3 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

3.1 Signal Validation

To validate the sensor data, the experimental setup with a transparent upper mold was used. The resin flow is recorded by a camera mounted above the tool and by the embedded acceleration sensors simultaneously. The propagating resin will introduce an impulse on the sensors, which is assumed to be visible in the recorded acceleration data. Furthermore, the integrated temperature sensor should detect a rise of temperature as the resin was heated prior to injection. In addition, to ensure that the time series of the video and the sensor data are synchronized, defined impacts were applied to the tool. Thus, signals recorded during the process can be correlated with process states for signal validation.

3.2 Process Monitoring

Subsequently, the sensor system was used in the second RTM tool to monitor resin flow fronts for varying experimental setups. Different manifestations of the flow front propagation were realized by

altering the sprue position. A temperature difference between sensors and resin was generated by heating the tool as well as the sensors to 65 °C and injecting the resin which is heated at room temperature.

The necessary sensitivity of the sensors to detect the flow front has to increase with decreasing resin velocity and temperature difference between the resin and the sensors. The first process configuration generates ideal conditions for a flow front monitoring system, see Fig. 4 a. The sprue is positioned in the corner of the tool and the fabric was tailored so that the edges of the cavity are not covered. This generates race tracks – channels of low flow resistance – which in turn leads to a higher permeability in these areas. Therefore the resin is expected to propagate quickly and exert a high impulse on the sensors while still having a low temperature compared to the sensors. A clear deviation both in the acceleration as well as in the temperature signal is expected as the resin passes the sensors in the sequence 3-2-1.

To move away from these ideal conditions, the second process configuration, as showed in Fig. 4 b, generates another scenario. The sprue is chosen to be central, so the resin encounters an area of high fiber volume content after injection. This in turn leads to a high flow resistance, minimizes the resin's velocity and ultimately results in a low impulse transferred to the sensors. Additionally, the temperature difference is going to be attenuated or even eliminated due to the long residence time of the resin in the hot mold. The ring gate will produce a circular spread of the resin which should at first reach the middle sensor (2), followed by a simultaneous detection by the two external sensors (1 and 3).

Fig. 4 Sprue positions with expected resin flow

4 RESULTS

4.1 Signal Validation

Fig. 5 shows the recorded acceleration data of the validation experiment in flow direction plotted over time. For better visibility, any offset of static acceleration, due to imperfect orientation of the sensors, has been subtracted from the data. The acceleration already displays a clear picture of how the resin propagates through the textile. At $t_1 = 75$ s, sensor 1 detects an interaction with the resin first, clearly visible by the drop in acceleration of respective sensor. A smaller but yet significant change in acceleration of sensors 2 and 3 seems consequential, since the sensors are connected through the PCB. When the resin propagates further, the acceleration measured by sensor 1 slowly returns to its initial value. That suggests that the arriving flow front tipped the sensor. After equilibrium of forces is restored, the sensor falls back to its original orientation. At $t_2 = 78$ s, a peak in the recorded acceleration of sensor 2 can be seen, indicating the arrival of the flow front. At $t_3 = 83$ s, sensor 3 shows a significant dent in its acceleration signal, which can be interpreted as the resin reaching the last of the sensors. Additional information can be drawn from the temperatures measured by the MEMS, displayed in Fig. 6 over the course of time. The temperature measurement has a ± 2 K error on the hardware side due to resolution limitations. Consequently, the temperatures are not displayed as absolute values, but instead relative to the respective initial temperature set to zero to accentuate the measured temperature changes. At the identified points in time $t_1 - t_3$ the respective sensors show concordantly to the acceleration signal a significant rise in temperature, as the preheated resin passes

by.

This information corresponds well with the process states extracted from the visual data, see Fig. 7. The observed times for the resin passing the respective sensors are $t_1 = 75$ s, $t_2 = 78$ s and $t_3 = 83$ s. Furthermore, the irregular data occurring after the resin passed the last sensor can be explained using the video. The force resulting from the dynamic pressure of the propagating resin surpasses the tool's clamping force on the textile at $t_4 = 87$ s and leads to a translational movement of the fabric inside the tool. This is pronounced in several peaks throughout the signals. At $t_5 = 91$ s, air enters the cavity through the sprue. This results in a series of high frequency vibrations as air bubbles excite the PCB and sensors.

Fig. 5 Accelerations in flow direction of three consecutive sensors during resin injection of the validation experiment

Fig. 6 Measured temperatures of three consecutive sensors during resin injection of the validation experiment

Fig. 7 Sensors and propagating flow front in transparent mold

4.2 Process Monitoring

After validating the sensor network's capability of detecting flow fronts, the data recorded with the second RTM setup is analyzed.

Out-of-plane acceleration and temperature data of the first process setup are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. The offset of the data was eliminated to better highlight essential effects. The first glance at the acceleration data already shows high peaks. This coincides with our expectation of a quickly spreading resin flow that hits the sensors with high energy. Sensor 3 is reached by the resin first and shows a significant rise in acceleration at $t_1 = 55$ s. Contrary to the presumption it is not sensor 2 but sensor 1 that is reached by the resin afterwards at $t_2 = 60$ s. This behavior is thought to be caused by a decentered positioning of the fabric inside the tool. Already a slight deviation leads to a shift of flow paths. In this case, the textile may have been placed too far to the lower right, decreasing the flow resistance for the counterclockwise racetrack and increasing it in clockwise direction. Consequently, the resin velocities differ and instead of meeting opposite to the sprue, the flow fronts collide alongside the lower edge of the cavity. This explanation matches with sensor 3, positioned at the lower edge of the cavity, being the last sensor to see the flow front. By looking at the temperature data in Fig. 9 this theory can be confirmed, as the significant drops in temperatures correspond with the peaks detected in the acceleration data as seen in Fig. 8. The experiment's observation yields a sequence of risers being filled with resin, which corresponds to this assumption.

Fig. 8 Out of plane accelerations of three sensors during resin injection with corner sprue

Fig. 9 Measured temperatures of three sensors during resin injection with corner sprue

Fig. 10 shows the out of plane acceleration data for the second process configuration with a corner sprue and Fig. 11 the respective temperatures, each plotted over time. Both the acceleration's, as well as the temperature's offsets are zeroed. As the residence time of the resin inside the tool now is longer, the temperature difference between resin and sensors is eliminated completely. The measured temperature data does not show any change of temperature except the mentioned inaccuracies due to limitations in the sensor's resolution. Hence no information about the flow front can be excerpted from the temperature data. The acceleration data, however, still shows significant peaks that can be correlated with the flow front. The acceleration peaks in this setup have higher values: There was more energy transmitted by the resin which indicates a faster propagating flow front. The central sensor, sensor 2, has the least distance to the sprue and therefore is the first to detect the propagating resin at $t_1 = 62$ s. The moving resin tilts the sensor, leaving an offset in acceleration after the first contact. Instead of a simultaneous detection by the remaining sensors, however, the resin reaches sensor 1 ($t_2 = 80$ s) before sensor 3 ($t_3 = 84.5$ s). This divergence from the presumption can be traced back to the stacking sequence of the laminate. The permeability along the main fiber orientation is higher than perpendicular to it [6]. Consequently, the top layer's $+45^\circ$ orientation generates a flow channel of lower flow resistance from the sprue towards sensor 1. This in turn leads to the measured resin propagation with sensor 1 being hit by the resin before sensor 3. The experimental observation agrees with the measured propagation, as the sequence of risers filled with resin match up with the measured acceleration peaks.

Fig. 10 Out of plane accelerations of three sensors during resin injection with central sprue

Fig. 11 Measured temperatures of three sensors during resin injection with central sprue

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The sensor network used in the scope of this work measures acceleration and temperature at three different positions. Through visual validation it was possible to correlate peaks in acceleration and changes in temperature to the passing of a resin flow front. Furthermore, the experiment yielded that additional events can be detected. Infiltrated air and movement of the fabric were visible in the captured acceleration data. However, the features for those events are not manifested clearly and need further investigation to be processed properly. A second test setup showed that the sensor network can be used for processes with different boundary conditions. Fast spreading resin was able to be detected by the accelerometer unambiguously, and even in areas of high flow resistance, peaks in the acceleration data gave insight into the resin's propagation inside the tool. The benefit of the temperature sensor, however, is closely linked to the setup present. Only if the initial temperature difference of resin and sensors – or the flow front velocity – is high enough, the resin propagation is detectable in the sensor's temperature data.

The system showed a high potential for further and more detailed investigations. Comparing the sensor data with a-priori knowledge could allow to deduce the fiber orientation present or to validate the correct positioning of the fabric inside a tool. Concurrently, if fit to a standardized process, the system could detect unwanted deviations such as altering fiber volumes, race tracks or variations in process temperatures. Another potential lies in the detailed analysis of the resin's impact on the sensors. Based on the sensor's exact movement, a mesoscopic flow front measurement could be realized. A permeability gradient over the laminate's thickness direction could be calculated, which would be of great interest for the validation of flow simulations.

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